

EARTH SCIENCES

AEROSPACE RESEARCH IN AZERBAIJAN AND WITHIN THE SCIENCE OF GEOGRAPHY

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Abstract

Recently, space research, or in other words the method of remote sensing of the natural environment, has been widely used. The essence of this method is that the object under study is monitored without direct contact using equipment installed on aircraft, helicopters, artificial Earth satellites or spacecraft. Electromagnetic waves emanating from and reflected by the Earth's surface are received and highly accurate information about the natural environment is collected. These waves vary greatly in their physical properties. Each object on the Earth's surface is known to have its own specific radiation emission and reflection capabilities. All these characteristics create favourable conditions for using modern aircraft to study the natural environment in great detail and to use it more efficiently.

The concept of "aerospace research" is a broad, multidisciplinary and high-tech scientific field that encompasses aeronautics and space technologies. Aerospace research is a scientific and technical field that deals with the design, development and use of objects that move inside and outside the Earth's atmosphere - aircraft, satellites, spacecraft and other aerospace technologies.

Aerospace research in Azerbaijan has been a developing field in recent years, covering satellite technologies, Earth remote sensing and space science.

Keywords: Aerospace, Azerbaijan, geographical, research, satellite.

Introduction

One of the major innovations in the development of geographical science in the 20th century was the emergence of the aerospace method, which allows the study of the Earth from space. In many cases, this method is also recognised as a separate scientific field - space geography.

The study of the Earth's surface from a distance - i.e. using aeroplanes, helicopters, artificial satellites, spacecraft and other means located beyond the Earth's surface - is known as the method of space research. The application of this method, which provides extensive geo-information data, has breathed new life into our science, revitalising it and enabling exploration of the deepest levels of knowledge.

Main Part

The range of research carried out using aerospace information tools is quite broad. One of the main areas of focus is the relief of the Earth's surface. A number of geomorphological processes occurring on a global scale, the relationship between relief and geological structure, and the role of endogenous and exogenous processes in the formation of relief can be more effectively identified through aerospace imagery. Such imagery can be used to produce geomorphological maps of hard-to-reach areas at various scales, and to make significant corrections to existing maps.

Aerospace research methods also play a crucial role in detecting and predicting spontaneous natural phenomena such as floods, landslides, avalanches and similar processes. Due to certain characteristics, areas in deserts where groundwater is close to the surface can be more easily identified using space-based instruments. This in turn helps specialists to successfully solve the problem of water supply in these regions.

The role of space-based information tools in vegetation studies is indispensable. Traditional methods

face major challenges in surveying high mountain meadows, wetlands, tundra vegetation and the vast expanses of taiga forests. Aerial imagery makes it easy to monitor these regions, assess the biological productivity of hayfields and pastures, and effectively track the spread of pests and plant diseases.

Various changes in agricultural crops related to shifts in water and nutrient regimes are easily detected using aerial imagery, allowing timely recommendations to be made to stabilise crop productivity. Operational data on snow cover and glaciers help to determine the water content of snow, its height in mountainous areas and its potential impact on river flow during the summer months. Measures are being developed to prevent water being wasted during spring floods and to make irrigation more efficient. Aerial imagery is also used to monitor the dynamics of glaciers in mountainous regions and assess their role in the hydrological regime of the area.

Space images taken at different times can be used to monitor water level fluctuations in water bodies, the resulting deformation processes, potential damage to agriculture, turbidity levels in rivers and lakes, and various changes in the chemical composition of the water. These indicators can be used to determine the degree of water pollution. The effects of wind, gravity waves and tsunamis on the ocean surface can cause water levels to rise by between 1 and 20 metres. If these are not constantly monitored by aerospace research, they can cause significant damage to agriculture. At present, laser beams from artificial satellites are widely used to record ocean and sea waves. The most advantageous feature of these methods is that they allow research to continue under any meteorological conditions (Həsənov T., Hacıadə Ə. 2001).

At present, the surface temperature of the world's oceans is also successfully measured by space instruments, which makes it possible to study the nature of the currents that occur in oceans and seas. At the same time, it supports the fishing industry. The development of space technology also offers great potential for measuring the salinity of the world's oceans.

Azerbaijan has been using space research materials since the 1970s. After Moscow, the first such initiative in Baku was in 1974, when the Institute of Space Research of Natural Resources under the Academy of Sciences of the Azerbaijan SSR was established under the leadership of Acad. T.G. Ismayilov. At that time, the Institute focused on studying the geological structure and mineral resources of the Caucasus-Caspian region, forest and soil cover, as well as issues related to the hydrosphere and environmental protection. This organisation has since evolved into the Azerbaijan National Aerospace Agency and continues to operate under this name. Geography-related research at the Agency is carried out by the Institute of Ecology. This institute plays an important role in the study of natural-territorial complexes and in forecasting through the use of space-based geoinformation (Mehdiyev A.Ş., İsmayilov A.İ. 2011).

At present, the Institute has 6 departments and 8 laboratories. These structural units are engaged in the study of harmful processes of natural and anthropogenic origin occurring in the atmosphere, water bodies, soil and vegetation cover. As a result of the research carried out, important issues such as the prevention of natural destructive processes - floods, landslides, avalanches, etc. - have been studied and specific recommendations have been made to the competent authorities. The results of these studies have been recognised and approved by UNESCO, Intercosmos and other organisations.

The establishment of the "Laboratory for Application of Aerospace Methods in Geography" under the Institute of Geography of the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences in 1977 played a significant role in the expansion of aerospace research. Aerospace methods are particularly important in geomorphology and landscape studies, which are among the key branches of physical geography. Based on the comparison of space images taken at different times, a complex network of regular patterns corresponding to the tectonic faults of the eastern part of the Greater Caucasus and the Azerbaijani part of the Lesser Caucasus was identified. On the basis of spatial analyses carried out in these areas, large and small-scale morphostructural maps were made. All these studies on spatial resources were thoroughly analysed and comprehensively summarised in the monograph "The morphostructural structure of Azerbaijan and the surrounding mountainous areas" (Həsənov T., Hacızadə Ə. 2001).

The study of Azerbaijan's landscapes with the help of space-based research materials has expanded considerably. Initially, these studies focused on the southern slopes of the Greater Caucasus and the low mountainous areas of the Ajinohur-Jeyranjol regions. As a result, patterns of spatial distribution of anthropogenic land-

scapes and their structural characteristics were identified. Landscape units (type-semi-type valleys) and landscape type maps were prepared on the basis of black and white aerial photographs (İsmayilov A.İ, 2004).

Based on the use of decoded space imagery, the influence of recent tectonic movements and morphostructures of the Lesser Caucasus on the formation of modern landscapes has been clarified. Space research has also been used to study and map other physical-geographical processes, such as the formation of floodplains, the dynamics of exogenous processes and their spatial distribution. Satellite images were used to analyse the condition and current development dynamics of agro-irrigated landscapes, and a map of agro-irrigated landscapes on the right bank of the Kura River was prepared (Həsənov T., Hacızadə Ə. 2001). These materials have also been used to study the landscapes of Azerbaijan's mud volcanoes.

Various economic geographical studies have also been carried out using aerospace methods. However, the research conducted in this direction in our republic cannot be considered satisfactory. Extensive work is currently being done to study the water resources flowing into Azerbaijan from the border areas and neighbouring republics. It has been found that rivers flowing from Armenia - such as the Araz, Okjuchay, Debet, Agstafachay, Tovuzchay and others - are heavily polluted. Concentrations of certain substances (Ca, Na, HCO₃, NH₃, etc.) exceed international standards by up to 10 times. In addition, the Agency's institutes have initiated scientific research on environmental issues such as soil contamination with oil products, salinisation and flooding in the Absheron region. In addition, the Department of Cartography has begun studies on the creation and analysis of ecological and topographic maps of the Absheron Peninsula using aerospace materials (Mehdiyev A.Ş. 1998).

Thus, as we can see, aerospace methods make it possible to further expand the scope of research on Azerbaijan's natural, ecological and economic-territorial-settlement-communication systems.

Currently, the Azerbaijan National Aerospace Agency is the state institution responsible for managing Azerbaijan's space research programmes. The main projects of the Agency are as follows

- Azerspace-1 (in cooperation with Azercosmos)
- Azersky
- Azerspace-2 (in cooperation with Azercosmos)

The organizations operating under the Agency include the following:

- Institute of Space Research of Natural Resources
- Scientific Research Institute of Aerospace Informatics
- Institute of Ecology
- Experimental Plant for Space Instrumentation
- Special Design Bureau for Instrumentation
- Special Design-Technological Bureau (located in the city of Lankaran)

Conclusion

Research using space-based information is much cheaper, faster and more accurate than studies carried out using traditional methods. It is possible to obtain precise data on natural processes over large regions of the Earth in a short time.

At the same time, the wider use of space information in agriculture and scientific research has not only been fully justified in terms of economic efficiency, but has also more than compensated for the costs incurred by humanity in exploring space.

Thus, the underuse of space information in agriculture and scientific research represents a significant loss. Currently, space imagery is widely used in fields such as agriculture and forestry, construction, meteorology, environmental studies, communication systems, ecology, geodesy and cartography, and natural resource studies. The use of space information has laid the foundation for the planned and comprehensive study of the Earth's nature, the planet itself and the surrounding areas.

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